

Constructivist didactic strategies in Electronics Laboratory practices in Engineering students.

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ABSTRACT: Under the premise that didactic strategies constitute an organized structure that contributes to the generation of effective learning processes, research was conducted using documentary and field research designs. The research scope was descriptive and cross-sectional. The survey technique was employed, and the survey was conducted among a population of 81 individuals from the field of electronic engineering. This population was determined through non-probabilistic intentional sampling and consisted of graduates who had used the Communication Networks Laboratory in the last 4 academic periods.

Among the findings, it was observed that approximately 72% of the surveyed population mentioned that teachers primarily engage in traditional lecturing as their teaching method. Likewise, nearly 65% of the study's population stated that teachers face limitations in applying active methodologies based on constructivism, such as Problem-Based Learning.

The conclusion drawn from this research is that teachers who conduct practical classes should significantly improve the utilization of didactic strategies aligned with constructivism. These methodologies will enhance the teaching and learning processes in the Communications Laboratory.

Limitation: The article points out limitations in the field design, as the surveys were administered to graduates rather than enrolled students, resulting in only 81 responses. It is suggested that alternative technological resources be explored to improve data collection.

Keywords: Active Methodologies, Constructivist, Didactic Strategies, Effective Learning, Research.

[Introduction](#)
[Literature review](#)
[Methodology](#)
[Discussion](#)
[Conclusion](#)
[Limitations](#)
[Recommendations](#)
[Disclosure Statement](#)
[References](#)

1. Introduction

The challenges currently demanded by 21st-century higher education emphasize the centrality of the student, who becomes the focal point. The level of student learning achievement relies on the use of learning strategies that provide them with the ability to meet the demands of a rigorous competency-based curriculum in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and the subsequent demands of contemporary society. According to García Gajardo et al. (2015), there are still groups of educators who encourage rote learning, leading to limited skill development. Therefore, it is essential to investigate whether students truly possess the tools to engage with new forms of learning. Consequently, it is necessary to influence teaching practices to ensure that didactic strategies become essential procedures in the teaching process, laying the foundation for efficient learning. Jara Conohuilca (2021) suggests that, in this context, it is essential to explore whether educators have pedagogical alternatives or a wide repertoire in their toolkit to facilitate a proper teaching-learning process in HEIs.

In addition to this reality, it is common to discuss innovation and educational improvement in the teaching and learning processes. However, the implications of this are a recurring theme in educational literature, especially as technological advancements continue, and knowledge areas strive to adapt to new requirements. The rapid pace of change does not always allow humans to adapt easily. As illustrated by Suárez-Escalona et al. (2023), in the educational sector in recent years, it has become common to observe the redesign of undergraduate and postgraduate educational programs in response to the evolving and volatile job market we are experiencing, aiming to align educational offerings with the demands of the job market.

When discussing classroom learning, various learning theories are included, which have developed in education due to different circumstances or conditions in methodological, emotional, motivational, physical, and other areas. These variables make learning multifactorial and complex (Castro Pérez & Morales Ramírez, 2015). Consequently, there is a range of learning theories that can be used in the processes through which humans learn effectively. In this regard, it is important to consider the learning processes that teachers use and ensure they are compatible with one or more learning theories (Perico-Granados et al., 2022). Often, this relationship is not explicitly established, and therefore, learning theories merely allow the interpretation of phenomena that take place in the classroom.

In this context, the study of learning theories provides a broad vocabulary and a conceptual framework to interpret various types of learning. Additionally, they offer practical solutions for the issues that arise in daily practice. Thus, it is essential to define the importance of didactic strategies in the educational process to discard outdated educational paradigms that have hindered the development of knowledge. Didactic strategies grounded in constructivism motivate students and energize the learning process, preparing students for the proper development of competencies in their respective disciplines through active methodologies (Chavez et al., 2016). These strategies view learning as a constructive process, and nowadays, these activities refer to operations that facilitate various school learning processes (Jones et al., 2022).

These approaches are based on Piaget, who posited that learning is a personal construction of the individual and true learning must be meaningful, as stated by Ausubel. In this regard, these principles should be considered as basic theoretical elements of the pedagogical strategies proposed in this document. These premises involve teachers and students actively in the learning process by engaging in active learning methodologies, where they seek answers to questions or hypotheses raised about phenomena in society or nature. Subsequently, through methodological processes, they provide concrete solutions.

This reality allows the school community to reflect on what, how, and why they are learning. To achieve this, it is considered that a well-designed teaching process should enable students to acquire knowledge that equips them to tackle various situations and practical cases (Ruiz-Campo et al., 2022). In other words, the ultimate goal is to create a solution to the problem posed by the teacher. Therefore, these actions that the teacher applies intending to provide learning to their students are called pedagogical strategies.

The Department of Electrical and Electronics at the Universidad de las Fuerzas Armadas ESPE, Latacunga Campus, has 13 laboratories for conducting various laboratory practices in the fields of Electrical, Electronics, Automation, and Communications. The subject of this research is the Communications Laboratory, which serves the Electronics and Automation program.

For the development of practices, the laboratory is equipped with digital and analog modulation simulation platforms, equipment for implementing both wireless and wired data networks, as well as measurement equipment such as signal generators, spectrum analyzers, oscilloscopes, and multimeters. It also provides support for undergraduate and postgraduate thesis projects and research projects proposed by the university and research groups. These projects aim to evaluate connectivity between different electronic devices or radio spectrum analysis (Franco Román & Sánchez Tapia, 2021).

Regarding the development of teaching activities in the laboratory, it is evident that there are not enough pedagogical alternatives for educators to improve the teaching and learning processes in the Communications Laboratory. The experimental work is not focused on helping students acquire skills in handling the instrumentation and scientific skills. It is essential to establish strategies and pedagogical techniques that encourage the connection between theory and experiment, as an indissoluble relationship between them cannot be allowed.

The teacher should not only work on theory or just in the laboratory; the professional must strike a balance between the two components that make up the teaching and learning process. This point of equilibrium is essential for achieving significant achievements in the classroom, contributing to comprehensive education. In this sense, both components must be closely linked, and strategies and techniques must be a two-way interaction between theoretical elements and practice. The educator decides what is essential for the student to learn based on their extensive knowledge, thereby avoiding falling into old practices of traditional lectures. There are also alternative methods that can be included, such as those related to a trial-and-error approach, which encourage students to work autonomously based on theory and then apply it during the corresponding practices (Miranda Fernández &

Andrés, 2009); (Calderon et al., 2017). The teacher must guide their laboratory work toward problem-solving in a real context.

Given the aforementioned reality, there is an interest in identifying the portfolio of didactic strategies and techniques used, such as masterful strategies, group strategies, individual strategies, audiovisual techniques, written techniques, and verbal techniques, among other alternatives that the teacher can employ for the development of their classes in the Communications Laboratory. This is done to determine whether the inclusion of new alternatives is necessary for the improvement of the educational process.

Furthermore, it should be noted that there is a lack of resources and adequate equipment. If the laboratory does not have the necessary resources and equipment to conduct practices and experiments, students will not be able to develop the necessary skills and abilities. In addition to this, there is a lack of training in topics related to the use of didactic strategies and techniques for teachers and laboratory technicians.

2. Literature Review

Didactic strategies applicable in the Communications Networks Laboratory.

Didactic strategies are procedures, resources, or teaching methods employed by the teacher based on planning, supported by teaching techniques. These procedures and resources are used by the teacher to achieve significant learning, intentionally facilitating deep and conscious knowledge processing.

There are critical elements that contribute to the quality of education for future engineers at the University, and one of these elements is the inclusion of didactic strategies to transform the laboratory into a place where theory effectively merges with practice. Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to constantly incorporate different alternatives into their classes. These options allow students to significantly benefit from the teaching-learning process, guiding students toward critical and reflective thinking. By avoiding the old practice of merely "listening," teachers should include alternative methods of conveying the message, incorporating visual and practical elements. These alternatives facilitate improved learning processes (López et al., 2017). In this context, some strategies can be adapted to practical settings in laboratories, such as inquiry-based learning, problem-based learning, project-based learning, exercise workshops, peer learning, and cooperative learning (Tandazo & Molina, 2019).

In this line of thought, it is essential to mention that a strategy is demonstrated through techniques and procedures that may vary depending on the subject and the topic being taught. However, they ultimately converge toward the same goal, which is to achieve a predefined objective in micro-curricular planning. Pedagogical strategies can employ various techniques, applied individually or collectively (López et al., 2017). In this sense, strategies function as an organized structure contributing to the design of effective learning processes. These strategies are grounded in a constructivist model, prioritizing learning through understanding, which promotes knowledge construction in the learner. This way, students don't merely reproduce knowledge; they process it to build new knowledge,

fostering analytical skills, interpretation through synthesis, critical thinking, and deductive and inductive reasoning, among other cognitive abilities (Campos-Gutierrez et al., 2021).

Types of didactic strategies for use in the Communications Laboratory

Grounded in active methodologies proposed by Ausbel, active methodologies contribute to the development of the teaching and learning process and engage the teacher in a proactive role in the classroom, serving as a support element in the process. This is achieved through activities and procedures that promote autonomous learning by having students confront realities that require the construction of knowledge and the development of competencies, enabling students to be part of cognitive learning societies and communities. This reality transforms the learner into an active participant in the learning process, contributing to the enhancement of thinking skills (Guamán Gómez et al., 2022); (Luy-Montejo, 2019).

There are active methodologies that can be applied in engineering practices, methodologies that seek to implement new strategies in line with the professional and social demands in an ever-changing environment. One of these strategies is Problem-Based Learning (PBL), which aims to develop generic competencies by promoting interdisciplinary work in the classroom to solve problems. This is achieved through organization, planning, analysis, and synthesis (Fernández & Duarte, 2013). These actions encourage students to prepare themselves based on real, simple, and complex problems that are equivalent to what they will encounter in their student, professional, and social lives.

Problem-based learning (PBL) allows theoretical knowledge to be applied in practice, motivating student-centered learning that closely aligns with their professional performance. PBL promotes information retrieval by students, facilitating the opportunity to interact with different academic disciplines through the acquisition of knowledge in other subjects. This approach encourages problem-solving, knowledge integration, the development of research skills, collaborative work, and the promotion of values such as responsibility, honesty, and cooperation. Additionally, this strategy leverages virtual and computational didactic tools, facilitating and improving the teacher-student relationship (Guamán Gómez et al., 2022) (Flórez-Nisperuza et al., 2021).

Similarly, in the words of Dewey, who emphasizes that students can learn by doing, Project-Based Learning (PBL) involves identifying problems observed in a specific context. This issue motivates collaborative work to propose one or more research designs, which must be executed methodically and systematically, aimed at achieving specific objectives that need to be operationalized to accomplish the overall project goal. This didactic strategy intertwines two components: theoretical and practical elements. Both are necessary for the success of the project. Therefore, project participants need to have an identified theoretical foundation to transition to practical activities. It is also essential to emphasize the importance of students learning by doing, with teachers serving as guides in the teaching and learning process, promoting the development of this didactic approach, allowing students to connect with reality through direct experiences in their environment (Feeney et al., 2022) (Barrera Arcaya et al., 2022).

Another didactic strategy, based on the integration of the contributions of Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky's theories and rooted in constructivism, encourages social interaction, the exchange of ideas, and knowledge among group members. It is particularly suitable for promoting teamwork in the educational process in applied sciences. This strategy is known as collaborative work and fosters the development of competencies like teamwork, which has gained significance in recent years in the university context. This method promotes educational interaction between students and teachers. It is a didactic method that can be used in small groups where students work together to maximize their learning and that of their peers.

Collaborative learning, also known as peer or peer-to-peer learning, is based on the educational premise that the best teacher is another student, involving the direct participation of students that is properly guided and intentional (García Zapata et al., 2021). It's essential to mention that in the context of higher education, professors value and emphasize this strategy because it enhances a better understanding of the subject matter, improves group cohesion, and contributes to the development of critical reflective reasoning skills. Therefore, collaborative work is considered an interesting tool that facilitates the learning process.

Research evaluating the effectiveness of collaborative learning as a didactic strategy consistently points to its positive impact on the learning process. It's important to note that despite the advantages of this methodology, there is room for improvement in its implementation, organization, and assessment, which can potentially become disadvantages (García Zapata et al., 2021); (Rodríguez-Borges et al., 2020).

This article holds theoretical and practical significance because it is related to the educational environment and aims to identify pedagogical alternatives that benefit both teachers and students participating in the Data Network Systems Laboratory, part of the Communications Laboratory at UFA - ESPE. These strategies will serve to motivate and stimulate students' scientific interest by proposing active, visual, and practical strategies that enhance teacher-student interaction. This, in turn, motivates students to tackle the various challenges they encounter in their daily lives.

Furthermore, the contribution is educational, offering possibilities that benefit the participants in the educational process. For students, it will enhance their analytical and synthetic abilities, foster creativity, and enable the construction and application of knowledge in the field of applied sciences. For teachers, it will help alleviate difficulties that may arise in the educational process. The proposed didactic strategies will create a guiding framework that coordinates a set of techniques to achieve clearly defined learning objectives.

In the context of the problem, from a theoretical perspective, it is now time to establish the research objective: To determine the influence of constructivist didactic strategies on the teaching-learning processes in Electronics Laboratory practices in engineering students.

3. Methodology

Research Design

The research design was both documentary and field-based. Documentary research involved a meticulous review of primary sources through the examination of databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, ESCI, and Scielo, among others. Field research was conducted to collect primary data through surveys administered to students and teachers. The field study was carried out cross-sectionally. An instrument, validated by two experts with doctoral degrees in higher education, was used for data collection. The purpose of this validation was to ensure the content of the instrument was sound, thus establishing the reliability of the tool. Once the instrument was validated, Google Forms was used to gather the required information related to the application of didactic strategies in the communication networks laboratories at UFA-ESPE (Arias, 2012).

The research was quantitative, descriptive, and cross-sectional, focusing on the significance of applying didactic strategies from a constructivist perspective. The instrument was administered to 81 graduating students from the Electronics and Automation Engineering program at the Universidad de las Fuerzas ESPE Latacunga campus, using Google Forms, a tool sent via email.

Sample

The representative sample was selected through non-probabilistic purposive sampling, targeting graduating students who had used the Communication Networks Laboratory in the last 4 academic periods. Quantitative data analysis was conducted using the statistical software package SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

For the study of the didactic strategies variable, the Likert Scale was utilized. This scale analyzed various categories of the variable, including lecture-based strategies, group strategies, individual strategies, audiovisual techniques, written techniques, and verbal techniques. The study aimed to determine whether the inclusion of new alternatives was necessary for the improvement of the educational process.

Analyzing of Data

The variables proposed in this study are categorical and were processed using SPSS. The primary data derived from the administration of the closed questionnaire were obtained through the creation of frequency tables. These tables contain absolute frequencies, relative frequencies, and cumulative relative frequencies. Additionally, bar charts were used to visualize the data. The categories analyzed in the instrument were lecture-based strategies, group strategies, individual strategies, audiovisual techniques.

Results

As a result of applying the instrument to the students who have used the Communication Networks Laboratory, the main findings are presented below:

How often does the teacher use lecture-based strategies (lectures) in the development of the class in the Communications Laboratory?

Table 1: Lecture-Based Strategies

		Frecuency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Never	2	2,5	2,5	2,5
	Rarely	14	17,3	17,3	19,8
	Sometimes	26	32,1	32,1	51,9
	Almost always	26	32,1	32,1	84,0
	Always	13	16,0	16,0	100,0
	Total	81	100,0	100,0	

The presented results indicate that 2 students mentioned that the teacher never uses lecture-based strategies as part of an inquiry to gather information, and 14 students mentioned rarely. An equal number of students (26) mentioned that sometimes and almost always, and 13 students mentioned that the teacher always uses lecture-based strategies in the classroom. There are significant indications that around 72% of the studied population falls into the category of mentioning it.

These data suggest that teachers primarily rely on lecture-based strategies in the Communication Laboratory. The cited information indicates a missed opportunity to integrate theory with effective practical application, limiting students to passively "listening" and perpetuating traditional teaching methods. This situation reduces the chances for students to engage in critical and reflective thinking. Additionally, it constrains the possibility for teachers to introduce alternative approaches based on the constructivist model, which emphasizes understanding-based learning, allowing students to reproduce knowledge and actively construct new knowledge.

How often does the teacher use didactic strategies (Problem-Based Learning - PBL) in the development of the class in the Communications Laboratory?

Table 2: Didactic Strategies - Problem-Based Learning

		Frecuency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Never	25	30,9	30,9	30,9
	Rarely	28	34,6	34,6	64,2
	Sometimes	12	14,8	14,8	79,2
	Almost always	11	13,6	13,6	93,8
	Always	5	6,2	6,2	100,0
	Total	81	100,0	100,0	

Based on the obtained information, it can be indicated that for Problem-Based Learning (PBL) as a didactic strategy in class development, 30.9% of the students mentioned that teachers never use PBL, while 34.6% stated that teachers rarely apply PBL. Additionally, 14.8% mentioned that teachers sometimes use PBL. These results demonstrate that teachers do not frequently employ the didactic strategy of PBL in the development of the class in the Communications Laboratory.

Teachers face limitations in implementing active methodologies based on constructivism, with one such methodology being Problem-Based Learning (PBL). PBL aims to develop students' competencies related to interdisciplinary work within a classroom

setting where problems are presented, and students must find solutions through organization, planning, analysis, and synthesis. These practices motivate students to tackle both simple and complex problematic situations, similar to those they may encounter in their professional and social environments.

"How often are group strategies used by the teacher in the development of the class in the Communications Laboratory?"

Table 3: Pedagogical Strategies - Collaborative Work

		Frecuency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Never	2	2,5	2,5	2,5
	Rarely	12	14,8	14,8	17,3
	Sometimes	24	29,6	29,6	46,9
	Almost always	23	28,4	28,4	75,3
	Always	20	24,7	24,7	100,0
	Total	81	100,0	100,0	

Two students believe that the teacher never uses group strategies in their class hours, while twelve students express that these strategies are rarely used. Additionally, nearly equal percentages of "sometimes," "almost always," and "always," corresponding to 29.6%, 28.4%, and 24.7% respectively, indicate extensive application of didactic strategies related to collaborative work by the teacher for class development in the Communications Laboratory.

The integration of theoretical contributions from Piaget and Vygotsky, leading to the constructivist approach, is evident in collaborative work. This strategy has benefits such as social interaction through the exchange of ideas and improvement in the relationships among group members. This educational interaction between students and teachers allows for teamwork. It is important to mention that higher education teachers find it easy to apply collaborative strategies because they contribute to a better understanding of the topics, enhance group cohesion, and improve critical reflective reasoning skills (García Zapata et al., 2021); (Rodríguez-Borges et al., 2020).

4. Discussion

This section discusses the results or findings obtained by the authors and compares them with the results of other research related to the investigated topic.

(Jarama Luna & Matute Matute, 2013) concludes that an educational proposal supported by constructivism is essential when developing new educational tools that aim to implement innovative elements. In the survey work, the students' concerns about the use of new didactic resources became visible. In line with the authors, partial results from the applied survey show that 48.1% of the surveyed population mentioned that teachers use problem-based masterful didactic strategies in the Network and Communications Laboratory class; strategies based on constructivism.

In this context, (Metaute Paniagua et al., 2018) assert that the resulting didactic strategy should be oriented towards the formation of an engineer with freedom of thought, critical thinking ability, innovative and entrepreneurial vocation, ease of national and international mobility, physical and virtual interaction with peers, in line with the needs within a globalized context. They also emphasize the integration of theoretical and scientific foundations with creativity and practical innovation. The data obtained, it is stated that "almost always" and "always," equivalent to 29.6%, 28.4%, and 24.7%, respectively, indicate that the use of this collaborative work technique is highly effective for research development by the teacher in the Network and Communications Laboratory classroom.

(Herrera Tandazo, 2019) concludes that group strategy is used sparingly by teachers in the field of applied sciences, as during the academic year 2019-2020, they obtained an average usage percentage of only 58%. The strategies frequently used by teachers in that period were the masterful strategy with an average application percentage of 64% and the individual strategy with a 66% utilization rate that semester. When comparing the results obtained, it is observed that teachers providing classes in the Communications Network Laboratory use the Case Studies didactic strategy for class development. 34.6% of students state "almost always," and 14.8% state "always," but there is no majority of students indicate that teachers use Case Studies as a research tool for class development in the Communications Laboratory.

5. Conclusion

The following conclusions can be drawn from the investigative process:

According to the criteria of the cited authors, it is concluded that the pedagogical approach of constructivism enables students to achieve significant learning by constructing their knowledge through the application of active methodologies, such as collaborative work and Problem-Based Learning (PBL), among others. These methodologies result from the integration of theoretical contributions from Piaget and Vygotsky, which converge within the constructivist approach aimed at fostering freedom of thought, critical thinking, and innovative vocations.

The data obtained from the field study indicate that there is a lack of connection between theory and effective practice due to the limited use of active methodologies in the Communications Network Laboratory. This limitation is attributed to the presence of old traditional practices where students are passive listeners, which reduces opportunities for students to engage in critical reflective thinking. There is a significant need to enhance the application of didactic strategies oriented towards constructivism, as these methodologies can improve the research processes in the classroom.

The research has led to new questions about the proper use of didactic strategies in engineering laboratories. These questions should be further formalized and are associated with the content of this article. It is recommended to conduct research from the perspective of teachers, as this document is primarily based on the student's perspective. In the future, a more comprehensive perspective can provide valuable insights and propose solutions that benefit both teachers and students, ultimately enhancing the educational process.

Furthermore, it is essential to analyze the role of information technology tools and their contribution to the application of didactic strategies within the realm of virtual education in the field of communications networks in higher education.

6. Limitations

Specific limitations were encountered in the field design. When collecting information through surveys, it was not administered to students currently enrolled in the program to avoid potential negative impacts on the teacher-student relationship. Instead, it was administered to students who had graduated from engineering programs. However, for reasons unknown, only 81 individuals completed the survey. It is important to explore alternative technological resources for collecting the required information on this topic.

7. Recommendations

Identifying the limitations in the use of didactic strategies in the Communications Network Laboratory, it is essential to continue developing research related to pedagogical and didactic elements to improve the connection between theory and effective practice in engineering laboratories. These studies will provide a broader perspective on the identified issues.

It is also important to consider the inclusion of other research areas related to the educational process, such as educational technology. This can be achieved through the implementation of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), which are innovative tools that have transformed the way tasks are carried out in the current era. This inclusion will enable interdisciplinary research and contribute to enhancing the quality of education in higher institutions in the country.

8. Disclosure Statement

The authors did not report any potential conflicts of interest.

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